

Magnetic and Infrared Studies of Molecular Interactions

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From the measurement of the magnetic susceptibilities of some phenol-carbonyl systems, the paramagnetic contributions of the carbonyl groups were calculated. The frequency shifts and the changes in bond moment derivatives were calculated from infrared spectra of the above system. The similarities are brought out.

The magneto chemical investigation of several workers^{1,2} on the influence of the intermolecular interactions in liquids and solutions showed genuine deviations in many systems involving hydroxyl and carbonyl groups. These deviations can only be explained as arising due to molecular interactions in the systems. Jatkar *et al.*³ showed that these deviations can be correlated with $\Delta\nu/\nu$, where ν is the characteristic absorption frequency of the functional group in the infrared region. The present investigation is an attempt to correlate the spectral and magnetic behaviour of some carbonyl compounds in mixtures of phenol.

EXPERIMENTAL

The magnetic susceptibilities of the liquids and mixtures were determined by a perfected Gouy method⁴. The refractive index was determined for the D line using an Abbe's refractometer. The infrared spectra were recorded by a Hilger H 800 Spectrophotometer equipped with sodium chloride optical system, as given in detail in our earlier publication⁵.

RESULTS

The molecular susceptibilities for the pure liquids are given in Table I. The exaltations of the molar susceptibility of the mixture

$$\Delta\chi_M = \chi_{M(\text{exp})} - \chi_{M(\text{additive})}$$

is plotted against the concentration of the component liquids in Figure 1.

From the infrared spectra that were recorded for these systems the formation constants for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were determined. Using this, the individual spectra of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were calculated and the frequencies of the complexed C = O of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 were determined from the peaks of the calculated complex spectra. These values are given in Table II.

1. S. Hatem, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1951, **48**, 407; *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1949, 483.
2. W. R. Angus and W. K. Hill, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 923.
3. S. K. K. Jatkar, V. S. Jatkar and A. J. Mikhedkar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 465.
4. S. Sriraman, K. Ramaswamy and V. Shanmugasundaram, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1967, **64**, 952.
5. S. Sriraman and V. Shanmugasundaram, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1964, **37**, 395.

Fig. 1

TABLE I

No.	Compound	$\alpha \times 10^{24}$	$-\chi_d \times 10^6$	$-\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_p \times 10^6$	$\chi_p \times 10^6$ for COO group	Free (C=O) Frequency in cm^{-1}
1.	Methyl Acetate	6.97	51.94	42.37	9.57	9.57	1757
2.	Ethyl Acetate	8.84	64.06	54.39	9.67	9.37	1749
3.	Iso butyl Acetate	12.62	88.35	77.92	10.43	9.33	1753
4.	Amyl Acetate	14.10	99.06	88.26	10.80	9.60	1750
5.	Phenyl Acetate	14.73	101.30	81.96	19.34	8.40	1778
6.	Benzyl Acetate	16.63	113.30	92.50	20.80	9.56	1756

The molar susceptibilities are expressed in $\text{Cm}^3 \text{Mol}^{-1}$

TABLE II

No.	System Phenol with	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ Free in cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ (1 : 1) in cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ (1 : 2) in cm^{-1}	$\Delta\nu$ for 1 : 2 in cm^{-1}	χ_p	$\frac{(d\mu/dr)}{(d\mu/dr) \text{ free}}$ complexed	$\frac{\chi_p \text{ complexed}}{\chi_p \text{ free}}$
1.	Ethyl Acetate	1749	1731	1714	35	1.28	1.19	1.12
2.	Iso butyl Acetate	1753	1726	1715	38	1.64	1.21	1.14
3.	Amyl Acetate	1750	1728	1718	32	1.51	1.12	1.12
4.	Phenyl Acetate	1778	1754	1748	30	1.64	1.13	1.11
5.	Benzyl Acetate	1756	1731	1720	36	1.46	1.41	1.18

DISCUSSION

It is seen from Fig. 1, that the solute-solvent interaction modifies appreciably the diamagnetism of the phenol-ester systems and that, the exaltations are negative for all the mixtures. The paramagnetic term in the Van Vleck's expression of the molecular susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule depends on the deformability of the electron clouds, whereas the χ_d term is a function of the average dimension of the electron cloud. The results obtained can be explained as arising due to the formation of hydrogen bond, which introduces sufficient asymmetry by polarizing the functional group. The polarization of the functional groups could be calculated by the method of Dorfman⁶. According to this semi-empirical method,

$$\chi_M = -3.11 \times 10^6 \sqrt{k\alpha_0} + \chi_p$$

where k is the number of electrons, and $\alpha_0 \simeq \alpha$, the polarizability calculated from the molar refraction. From the measured χ_M values the χ_p value of the esters and hence the paramagnetic contributions of the $\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{array}$ group are calculated. These values of COO group along with the frequency of C = O in various esters are given in Table I. There seems to be a lowering of paramagnetism by one unit for COO group in the case of phenyl acetate. For all other esters almost the same paramagnetism is obtained. The infrared C = O frequency is also fairly constant in the region 1750 cm^{-1} for all esters while for phenyl acetate the C = O frequency is found at 1778 cm^{-1} . This relation between the infrared frequency and χ_p can be illustrated by another example. In methylethyl ketone the χ_p value of the C = O group is 10.20, whereas the substitution of an alkoxy group for the alkyl group results in a decrease of about one unit in χ_p value. In a similar way the carbonyl infrared frequency increases from 1728 cm^{-1} to 1750 cm^{-1} . This suggests that a frequency shift of 20 wavenumbers corresponds roughly to a change of one unit in Van Vleck paramagnetism. From the infrared data⁷ for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes, it was shown that the 1 : 2 complexes are relatively predominant even at 0.1M of phenol concentrations. This is in conformity with the Raman intensity studies by Taboury, Lecomte and Gray⁸ in binary systems involving phenol and carbonyl compounds.

A comparison of the χ_p values of the system (Table II) studied with the $\nu(\text{C} = \text{O})$ values of the 1 : 2 complex reveals that a shift of 20 wavenumbers of the characteristic frequency of the chromophor roughly corresponds to a change of one unit in the paramagnetic value. This result also confirms the view that the formation of 1 : 2 complex is more probable at high concentrations of phenol.

The infrared intensity changes are also indicative of the charge movements resulting in the distortion of the equilibrium configurations. So a comparison could also be made between the rate of change of bond moment, which is a function of the intensity changes, with the paramagnetic changes, since the paramagnetic changes are also indicative of the polarization of the functional group.

6. Ya Dorfman. 'Diamagnetism and Chemical Bond', American Elsevier Publishing Corporation, 1965, 159.
7. S. Sriraman and V. Shanmugasundaram, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1966, **39**, 1070.
8. F. J. Taboury, J. Lecomte and E. Gray, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1955, **51**, 245; *Compt. Rend.*, 1947, **224**, 907.

The $(d\mu/dr)$ values for the 1 : 2 complexed C = O and for free C = O were calculated by the method of Cole *et al.*⁹ and their ratios for the different systems are given in Table II. The ratio of the χ_p (complexed) with χ_p (free) is also calculated, where χ_p (complexed) is the paramagnetism exhibited by the complexed systems and χ_p (free) is that which should normally be present if there were no interactions. It is seen from the Table II that the magnitude of the two ratios representing the changes in bond moment and in paramagnetism show the same order of variation. But it should be made clear that the comparison is made between the changes in the rate of change of bond moment for C = O bond with the total change in paramagnetism of the system. Since the effect of H bonding of the O-H group on the magnetic susceptibility is extremely small, it is justified in regarding the total change in paramagnetism of the system as almost due to the polarization of the C = O bond.

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9. A. R. H. Cole, L. H. Little and A. J. Michell, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1169.